

Readme

Metadata for the Matlab workspaces that accompany the paper ‘Postquantum steering in scenarios with multiple characterised parties’.

These Matlab workspaces provide examples of assemblages in steering scenarios with multiple characterised parties (Bobs). Here we state how the variables in the workspaces relate to the mathematical objects defined in the manuscript.

- **Pax**: array that stores the values of the conditional probability distribution $p(\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{x})$.
 $p(\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{x}) = \text{Pax}(f(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{x}))$, where f is specified in Eq. (1).
- **RBk**: array that stores the values of the normalised conditional states $\rho_{\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{x}}^{(k)}$ for the k^{th} Bob.
 $\rho_{\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{x}}^{(k)} = \text{RBk}(f(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{x}))$.
- **SBk**: array that stores the values of the conditional states $\sigma_{\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{x}}^{(k)}$ for the k^{th} Bob.
 $\sigma_{\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{x}}^{(k)} = \text{SBk}(f(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{x}))$.
- **Rho**: normalised bipartite quantum states whose marginals yield $\rho_{\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{x}}^{(k)}$ as per Thm. 6 (if they exist).
 $\text{tr}_{\mathcal{H}_k} \text{Rho}(:, :, f(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{x})) = \rho_{\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{x}}^{(\neq k)}$, $k \in \{1, 2\}$.
- **Sig**: bipartite quantum states whose marginals yield $\sigma_{\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{x}}^{(k)}$ as per Thm. 6 (if they exist).
 $\text{tr}_{\mathcal{H}_k} \text{Sig}(:, :, f(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{x})) = \sigma_{\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{x}}^{(\neq k)}$, $k \in \{1, 2\}$.
- **rwhite**: robustness to white noise r^{w} .
- **rGHZ**: robustness to GHZ noise r^{GHZ} .
- **rW**: robustness to white noise r^{W} .
- **phi**: pure state used to generate ρ for the method of Prop. 8; $\rho = \text{phi}^\dagger \text{phi}$.

The enumeration of the indexes of the objects is given by:

$$f(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} a + |\mathbb{A}|(x - 1) & \text{for one Alice} \\ a_1 + |\mathbb{A}^1|(a_2 - 1) + |\mathbb{A}^1||\mathbb{A}^2|(x_1 - 1) + |\mathbb{A}^1||\mathbb{A}^2||\mathbb{X}^1|(x_2 - 1) & \text{for two Alices} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The rational approximations included in the scientific manuscript are computed via `sym(X, 'r')`, where `X` denotes the variable whose rational expression we want.